

SUSTAINING NIGERIAN TERTIARY EDUCATION IN A FUTURE PANDEMIC

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has substantially impacted higher education institutions globally, including Nigeria. This study seeks to explore ways to maintain the continuity of tertiary education in Nigeria in the event of future pandemics. The central research question addressed is "What measures can stakeholders in the Nigerian tertiary education system take to enhance its resilience in the face of future pandemics?" This research employs a comprehensive review of relevant literature to discuss fostering academic behaviors conducive to online teaching and learning during pandemics. The key findings emphasize cultivating effective academic behavior that encourages critical investment in online learning infrastructure. The study proposes specific and practical recommendations for stakeholders in Nigerian tertiary education, including technology investment and the adoption of best practices in teaching and learning. It offers valuable guidance for stakeholders in Nigerian tertiary education on how to prepare for and sustain education during future pandemics.

Keywords: Nigeria, Pandemic, Tertiary Institution

Introduction

The COVID-19 epidemic has had a significant impact on educational systems across the world, including Nigeria. The pandemic has hurt Nigeria's tertiary education system, which consists of universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education. The interruption of academic calendars is one of the COVID-19 pandemic's most important effects on Nigerian higher education. Nigeria, like many other nations, had to close its educational institutions to stop the virus's spread. All schools, including tertiary institutions, were ordered to close by the federal government in March 2020 (Nwachukwu, 2021). As a result, educational institutions' academic schedules were thrown off. For instance, the National Universities Commission (NUC) was forced to repeatedly push back the start of academic activities, and as of

January 2021, certain universities were still having difficulty finishing the 2019–2020 academic year (Ajiboye, 2021). The graduation of students and the advancement of academic personnel are both impacted by this delay.

The move to online learning is another effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on Nigerian tertiary education. Institutions had to discover ways to continue teaching and learning remotely after physical classrooms were closed. Online learning has become a popular method of carrying out academic programs at many Nigerian universities. The transition to online learning, meanwhile, was not without its difficulties. For instance, the inability of many students to enroll in online classes was caused by the lack of access to dependable internet connectivity, especially in rural locations (Akinwumi, 2020). Effectively implementing online

learning was another challenge for certain institutions due to a lack of technological infrastructure. In Nigeria, the digital gap was also made apparent by the change to online schooling, with some students having access to gadgets and internet connectivity while others did not (Ogunode, Abigeal, & Lydia, 2021). This digital divide can make it harder for some pupils to obtain school and limit their chances.

The COVID-19 pandemic also had an impact on the mental health of students and academic staff at Nigerian tertiary institutions. Many students and employees were cut off from their friends and coworkers due to the closing of institutions and the transition to remote learning, which could cause feelings of loneliness and despair (Habib, Dayyab, Iliyasu, & Habib, 2021). As a result of the epidemic, many people experienced stress and worry as they worried for their health as well as the health of their loved ones. Students and staff were already stressed and anxious, but the sudden switch to online learning and the difficulties that came with it made things even worse. The pandemic's effects on mental health have an impact on student's academic achievement as well as their general well-being in the tertiary education system.

The COVID-19 pandemic had an impact on tertiary education funding in Nigeria as well. The pandemic caused the Nigerian government's revenue to decline, which impacted its capacity to effectively fund education. To meet its financial obligations during the pandemic, the federal government had to reduce expenditures across all sectors, including education (Adeoye, Adanikin & Adanikin, 2020). The quality of education may suffer as a result of the financial cut, which may also reduce the resources available for research and innovation. The epidemic also had an impact on institutions' capacity to make money from extracurricular pursuits

like conferences, workshops, and seminars, which could further constrain their financial resources.

The COVID-19 epidemic also had an impact on how the research was done in academic institutions in Nigeria. Several research activities had to be suspended, and other research programmes had to be shelved entirely. Due to institution closures, researchers were unable to use the tools and resources they required to carry out their research (Ifijeh & Yusuf, 2020). Furthermore, some researchers were forced to change their priorities to focus on COVID-19-related research, which can have an impact on the continuation of present research programs. While COVID-19 research is crucial, it shouldn't come at the price of other crucial areas of study. In Nigerian institutions, the disruption to research efforts may limit their ability to contribute to the knowledge economy and innovation.

The COVID-19 epidemic affected academic staff employment in Nigerian tertiary institutions as well. Several academic staff members were unable to perform their teaching and research responsibilities as a result of the closure of several universities. As a result, some institutions were forced to enact wage reductions or put their employees on leave (Egielewa, Idogho, Iyalomhe, & Cirella, 2022). The pandemic also resulted in fewer academic job openings, which can hurt the career prospects of recent graduates.

The COVID-19 epidemic may hurt Nigerian tertiary education by raising the likelihood of student dropout rates. Some students may decide to leave their studies as a result of the change to online learning and its difficulties. Some students could find it challenging to engage in online classes due to a lack of consistent internet connectivity, devices, and electricity, particularly in remote locations. Also, the absence of in-person interactions with teachers and peers may make learning less interesting and

demotivate students (Ajiboye, 2021). The overall enrollment and completion rates of Nigerian higher institutions may be affected by the anticipated rise in student dropouts.

Challenges Faced by the Tertiary Education Sector in Nigeria During the COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disrupted the world's educational system, and Nigeria's tertiary education is no exception. University site closures, the shift to online learning, and the impact on institutional budgets are just a few of the difficulties that tertiary education, which includes polytechnics, colleges of education, and universities, has had to deal with since the epidemic.

The shutdown of campuses has been one of the biggest issues the Nigerian tertiary education system faced during the COVID-19 pandemic. As part of efforts to stop the virus's spread, the federal government ordered the closure of all postsecondary institutions in the nation in March 2020. (Adebayo, 2020). The shutdown, which lasted for several months, interfered with the academic schedule and caused exams and graduation ceremonies to be postponed (Nnabuko, 2020). This closure presented considerable difficulty for institutions that had to modify their academic calendars and make alternate arrangements for exams and graduation ceremonies, as well as students who could not complete their courses on time.

The transition to online learning has been a serious problem for Nigeria's tertiary education industry throughout the COVID-19 epidemic. Institutions were compelled to deploy remote teaching and learning techniques, like virtual classrooms and video conferencing, to ensure that students could continue their studies while campuses were closed (Kolo, 2020). However, the move to online learning has been tough for many students, especially

those from low-income backgrounds who do not have access to dependable internet connections, computers, or other necessary technologies (Ugwuanyi, 2020). Institutions have had to make investments in new technologies and platforms to support remote learning due to the absence of suitable infrastructure and equipment.

For professors who might not be accustomed to remote teaching techniques, the change to online learning has also presented difficulties. Many professors in Nigeria lack experience with online instruction and have been forced to swiftly adapt to new technologies and pedagogies (Jegade, 2020). Paraphrase to provide the additional help and resources our institution needs.

Another major issue facing Nigeria's tertiary education system is the financial burden brought on by the pandemic. Institutions have seen decreased revenue from tuition fees, lodging, and other forms of income as a result of the closure of campuses and the move to online instruction (Kolo, 2020). Due to this, it has become more challenging for institutions to fulfill their financial commitments, including personnel salaries and facility upkeep. There have been protests and strikes by employees and students as a result of many institutions having to reduce personnel or lay off workers to survive (Tobin, Okonofua, Adeke, & Obi, 2021).

The Nigerian tertiary education system faces structural and systemic issues because of the COVID-19 pandemic. For instance, the pandemic has highlighted the shortcomings of Nigeria's healthcare system, which has been overworked and underfunded for decades (Ebohon, Obienu, Irabor, Amadin, & Omoregie 2021). As a result, it has been challenging for universities to offer sufficient healthcare services for employees and students during the pandemic. The pandemic has also brought attention to the need for upgraded infrastructure in the Nigerian educational

system, especially dependable internet connections and access to technology (Adedeji-Adenola, Olugbake, & Adeosun, 2022). The efficient implementation of remote learning has been hampered by a lack of suitable infrastructure and resources, which made it challenging for institutions to meet the needs of professors and students.

Strategies Adopted to Mitigate the Effects of COVID-19 on Tertiary Education in Nigeria

The COVID-19 epidemic has had a huge influence on Nigeria's tertiary education industry, posing considerable hurdles in the form of campus closures, a move toward online education, financial strain, and the exposure of structural and systemic issues with the educational system. The Nigerian institutions and government adopted several initiatives to lessen these effects.

The Presidential Task Force on COVID-19 was established as one way the Nigerian government used to lessen the impact of COVID-19 on tertiary education. To coordinate the nation's reaction to the pandemic, including the response of the education sector, a task group was established (Obiakor & Adeniran, 2020). Guidelines for the secure reopening of campuses and the restart of academic activity were developed by the task group in close collaboration with tertiary institutions.

The transition to online learning was another tactic used by universities to lessen the impact of COVID-19. Institutions have made investments in new platforms and technology, like learning management systems and video conferencing tools, to promote remote learning (Chiedozie, Chukwuebuka, Chidimma, Onyinyechi, Chijioke, Chibuzor, & Chioma, 2021). Colleges also offered faculty members support and training to help them adjust to new teaching techniques (Akinwumi &

Itobore, 2020). This plan made it possible for students to finish their coursework and continue their studies even after campuses were closed.

Institutions also explored a range of measures to deal with the pandemic's financial hardship. While other colleges offered financial assistance to students who were having financial difficulties as a result of the pandemic, some implemented flexible payment arrangements for tuition prices (Kolo, 2020). Colleges also looked at alternative funding streams like research grants and collaborations with for-profit businesses (Akinwumi & Itobore, 2020).

The installation of health and safety procedures on campuses was another tactic used to lessen the impact of COVID-19 on tertiary education in Nigeria. These include establishing isolation facilities for pupils who tested positive for COVID-19, giving out face masks and hand sanitizers, and putting in place social distancing measures (Chiedozie et al., 2021). These steps assisted in keeping campuses secure for students, faculty, and staff as well as in halting the virus's spread.

Current State of Tertiary Education in Nigeria

Nigeria's tertiary education situation is a complicated and varied topic that needs to have all of its facets carefully examined (Ukeje, 2021). The standard of instruction and scholarly research in Nigerian tertiary education is one of the biggest problems there (National Universities Commission, 2021). The lack of skilled staff and sufficient funds for research at many Nigerian universities has caused the level of education to drop. Concerns have been raised concerning Nigerian graduates' capacity to compete in the international labour market as a result. Several universities have, however, made substantial strides in raising the caliber of their programs through efforts including curriculum reviews, faculty development,

and collaborations with foreign universities.

Governance is another factor that has an impact on tertiary education in Nigeria. Administrative and leadership issues, such as a lack of transparency, financial mismanagement, and political meddling, affect many colleges in Nigeria (Adesoji & Ajayi, 2021). The autonomy and independence of universities have been compromised as a result of the appointment of vice-chancellors and other important officials frequently based on political affinities rather than competence. More stakeholder involvement in university governance and the adoption of best practices in institutional management have been called for as solutions to this problem.

Another significant issue for Nigerian tertiary education is financing (Ukeje, 2021). Nigeria's public universities rely primarily on government funding, but it has historically been insufficient and unreliable, which has resulted in strikes and disruptions of academic activity. On the other hand, private universities mostly rely on tuition and other fees paid by students, which are sometimes out of the price range of many Nigerians. As a result, the gap between the rich and the poor in access to high-quality university education has widened. The public and commercial sectors have been urged to invest more in education, and alternative financing structures like endowments and philanthropy have also been suggested as solutions to this problem.

Finally, a crucial concern in Nigeria is access to postsecondary education (Ayoade, 2021). Although there are more universities and other educational institutions in Nigeria, many eligible applicants are still turned away due to a lack of space in the classrooms. Due to the high cost and limited accessibility of foreign universities, there is a significant demand for them in Nigeria. There have been suggestions for developing flexible

admissions procedures, expanding tertiary education infrastructure, and promoting online and remote learning as solutions to this problem.

Future Pandemic Preparedness in Nigerian Tertiary Educational Institutions

In Nigeria's tertiary institutions, the COVID-19 pandemic has brought attention to the necessity for efficient pandemic planning and response programs. The pandemic has severely disrupted academic activities, forcing many institutions to abandon traditional classroom instruction in favour of online instruction. To lessen the effects of potential pandemics, tertiary institutions must create and implement thorough pandemic preparation strategies.

The creation of online learning platforms is the first step towards becoming pandemic-prepared. Particularly since the COVID-19 epidemic, online learning has grown to be an essential part of postsecondary education. Around 1.2 billion pupils were affected by school closures worldwide, according to a UNESCO report, and many institutions switched to online education to maintain academic continuity. Nigerian tertiary institutions need to build reliable online learning environments that can sustain distance learning in the case of pandemics in the future. These platforms ought to be created so that students have access to educational resources, online classrooms, and communicative and collaborative tools. To accommodate students from different backgrounds and provide inclusive education, they should also be simple to use and accessible.

Moreover, backup plans must be created to ensure that academic activities continue in the event of a pandemic. These plans should specify clear criteria for the restart of academic activity and accommodate the particular demands of each institution (Gavi, 2021). Contingency

plans might, for instance, outline procedures for the use of physical separation barriers, the provision of personal protective equipment (PPE), and the execution of ongoing testing and contact tracing. Moreover, tertiary institutions can create backup plans that call for the adoption of alternative pedagogies like blended learning, which blends online and in-person instruction. To guarantee these contingency plans' efficacy in the face of fresh and developing pandemics, they must be periodically reviewed and updated.

The mobilization of resources is essential for pandemic preparedness. The tertiary institutions in Nigeria must raise funds to have the facilities and infrastructure needed to respond to pandemics. They are to give out personal protective equipment (PPE), hand sanitizers, and other essential supplies to avoid transmission of infectious diseases. To diagnose and cure infectious diseases, tertiary institutions should invest in the development of laboratory facilities. They can also spend money on studies that aim to provide vaccines and other treatments for newly emerging infectious diseases. Also, the Nigerian government must provide sufficient resources to aid tertiary institutions' preparedness and reaction operations (The World Bank, 2021).

Conclusion

The COVID-19 epidemic has disrupted several industries, including education. The pandemic posed several difficulties for the Nigerian tertiary education system, which saw considerable changes in teaching and learning techniques and the move to virtual learning. Many methods must be implemented to maintain the Nigerian tertiary education system in the event of a pandemic. The use of technology in the teaching and learning process is one approach that can be used. By ensuring that postsecondary institutions have operational e-learning systems that

can be used in the event of school closures, this strategy can be accomplished. A World Bank paper claims that by preserving learning continuity, technology might help lessen the detrimental effects of pandemics on education (World Bank, 2020). Making investments in research and development is another tactic.

Insights from research can help the Nigerian tertiary education system prepare for any pandemics in the future. In addition, it can aid in the creation of fresh approaches to assessment and instruction that address problems that arose during the pandemic. Collaboration between education sector stakeholders can also support Nigerian tertiary education in the event of future pandemics. The provision of essential resources and assistance to institutions during a pandemic can be ensured by cooperation between the government, tertiary institutions, and other pertinent organizations. This strategy can be implemented by creating regulations and guidelines that encourage cooperation and the formation of partnerships between stakeholders.

Finally, the COVID-19 pandemic has shown how much the Nigerian tertiary education industry needs to improve its readiness for pandemics in the future. To ensure the sustainability of tertiary education in Nigeria, it is imperative to pay urgent attention to and take immediate action in response to the challenges the sector faced during the pandemic, including campus closures, the switch to online learning, financial strains, and inadequate infrastructure. Institutions must invest in cutting-edge infrastructure and technologies to facilitate remote learning and teaching if they want to keep tertiary education in Nigeria going in the event of a pandemic. In addition to maintaining dependable internet connections, giving faculty members access to computers and other relevant technologies, and providing training and support so they can adjust to

remote teaching techniques, this investment must also contain these elements. Furthermore, to ensure that institutions have the resources needed to deliver high-quality education and retain their financial stability throughout upcoming pandemics, the government and the private sector must prioritize funding for tertiary education in Nigeria. To guarantee that universities are better equipped to provide healthcare services for students and staff during pandemics, this financing should also promote research and development in the healthcare industry.

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